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1. Introduction

Humans are continuously exposed to complex mixtures of diverse substances via the diet and environment. These compounds can either act independently or can interact and potentially affect human health. These possible interactions of substances in mixtures (additive, synergistic or antagonistic) can result in a lower or higher toxicity as expected from the single substances (Cedergreen 2014; Tallarida 2011). However, since the toxicological testing of pesticides for regulatory purposes is done with the individual substances, only limited data are available for possible mixture effects. Evidence for combination effects of pesticide mixtures has accumulated in the past years, predominantly in *in vitro* assays. Therefore, the toxicological analysis of mixture effects, especially by *in vivo* methods, is regarded an important task (Hass et al. 2007; Kortenkamp 2007; Kortenkamp et al. 2009). Aim of the EuroMix *in vivo* toxicity studies was to select three compounds A, B and C and to compare *in vitro* with *in vivo* data, to allow extrapolation from *in vitro* to *in vivo* findings and identify tests usable to assess further chemicals. Though leading to a similar adverse outcome, compound A and B should share a similar mode of action (MoA) whereas C should have a dissimilar MoA: this with the aim to also assess whether dose-addition applies for combined exposure to both compounds A and B and compounds A/B and C. Based on the multitude of possible combinations of pesticides to which humans can be exposed, the selection of substances to assess together is a major challenge. The selection of the compounds to be tested in the EuroMix *in vivo* toxicity studies is in Deliverables 3.2 and 3.3.

The following compounds (A, B and C) were chosen for toxicity testing *in vitro* and *in vivo*:

Endocrine effects, feminisation: linuron (androgen receptor agonist), flutamide (androgen receptor agonist), dienestrol (estrogen receptor agonist);

Craniofacial malformations: cyproconazole (hypothesised inhibitor of CYP26), triadimefon (hypothesised inhibitor of CYP 26), valproic acid (hypothesised inhibitor of HDAC);

Steatosis: Imazalil (hypothesised PXR, AhR, CAR, RAR agonist), thiacloprid (hypothesised PXR and PPAR γ agonist), clothianidin (hypothesised PPAR α antagonist).

This deliverable provides information on the study design and dosing of the EuroMix *in vivo* toxicity studies as well as descriptions of the used methods for the parameters tested and evaluated so far.

Furthermore, the results of the measured parameters are described, followed by a short conclusion and outlook.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Endocrine effects, feminisation

2.1.1 Animals and treatments

Sexually mature (90 days of age) female and male SD rats, from Charles River Laboratories (Sant Germain-L'Arbresle, France), have been used. Females have been housed 3 per group. After a 7-day acclimatisation period, the oestrous cycle was assessed during the following 10 days to ensure female regular cycles (4-5 days).

Then the rats have been distributed randomly over the different groups. The dams, the fathers and the pups have been individually and uniquely marked with ear cuts. At mating 2 females and 1 male rat have been used, then pregnant rats have been housed separately.

Groups included 4 female rats and 4 male pups per litter.

During treatment clinical and behavioural signs were monitored daily, while food and water intake and body weight determined 2 times per week.

Females were treated from gestation day (GD) 6 to post-natal day (PND) 21. The compounds were administered by *gavage* after being dissolved (0.2% ethanol) in commercial sunflower oil. Pups were sacrificed at post-natal days 21 (see figure 1).

Doses selection was based on available literature data. Flutamide and linuron single doses were selected on literature data (Foster and McIntyre, 2002) and data from pilot studies. The lowest and the maximal doses were chosen based on the same study. For flutamide all the doses selected from the study proved adequate (50, 25, 12.5, 6.25 mg/kg bw), and one lower dose was added to allow a better analysis of the dose-response curve (3.5 mg/kg bw). For linuron the two highest doses (50 and, 25 mg/kg bw) from literature were not adequate (lethality), so three lower doses were added in order to be able to better study the dose-response curve (6, 3, 1.5 mg/kg bw).

Single doses from dienestrol were not available so the criteria was based on diethylstilbestrol (DES) (Metzler and Fisher, 1981); the dose used on that study for DES were 200µg/kg bw i.v.(GD 13-20). After some trials in our laboratory that showed that the doses 200 and 100µg/kg bw produce abortions, the highest dose for the study was established at 75 µg/kg bw. However, 75 and 50 µg/kg bw resulting no viable animals, so doses of 12.5, 6.25, 3.125, 1.5, 0.75 and 0.37µg/kg bw were chosen (note that the dose of 12.5 resulted in the death of some animals).

For mixture experiments (binary mixtures) the doses used in the mixture was the half of the doses used in the single compound experiment: more accurate doses could not be chosen due to the high variability in the RPF calculations that lead to highly uncertain RPF and ED values. Since linuron had no effect (BMD analysis for Linuron across all PNDs gave flat curves) the only linuron dose in the mixtures was highest dose not causing lethality.

Treatment groups were as follows:

Flutamide: 3.5, 6.7, 12.5, 25 or 50 mg/kg bw (Sigma-Aldrich, purity ≥99%)

Dienestrol: 0.37, 0.75, 1.5, 3.125, 6.25, 12.5, 50, or 75 µg/kg bw (Sigma-Aldrich, purity ≥95%)

Linuron: 1.5, 3, 6, 12.5, 25, 50 mg/kg bw (Sigma-Aldrich, purity ≥98%)

Flutamide (mg/kg bw) + dienestrol ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw): 3.5+0.37, 3.5+3, 25+0.37, 25+3, or 25+1.5

Flutamide + linuron: 3.5+12.5, or 25+12.5 mg/kg bw

Dienestrol ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw) + linuron (mg/kg bw): 0.37+12.5, or 3+12.5

Control-oil (vehicle)

Control (without vehicle)

2.1.2 Parameters evaluated

The following parameters have been recorded: sex ratio at PND 1 and 4, anogenital distance at PND 1, 4, 7, 14, 21, cryptorchidism at PND 21, nipple retention at PND 14. Pups body weight was also recorded at PND 1, 4, 7, 14 and 21.

2.1.3 Tissue collection

At PND 21 both testes were removed and weighed. Then, testes were placed in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80°C for mRNA expression.

For gene expression analysis, total RNA was extracted according to the manufacturer's protocol (Qiagen, Cat No. 74136) from rat testis tissues. For first-strand cDNA synthesis, total RNA were reverse-transcribed into cDNA using the PrimeScriptTM RT reagent Kit- Perfect Real Time (Takara). Primers were designed using primer-BLAST (NIH, National Institute of Health) for selected endocrine genes. Six genes were tested, i.e. those that were selected after literature review, namely *Cyp11a1*, *Cyp17a1*, *Hsd3b2*, *Insl3*, *Pgr* and *Star*.

All genes were amplified by SYBR Green- based real-time PCR in the Step One Plus detection system (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Expression levels of the target genes were normalized to the reference gene *Gapdh*. Each cDNA was analyzed at least in triplicate by real-time PCR. Relative gene expression was calculated using the $\Delta\Delta\text{CT}$ method (Livak et al, 2001).

Statistics in comparison to control were assessed by the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test followed by Dunn's test, using GraphPad Prism v.8 (GraphPad Software, La Jolla, USA). A p value < 0.05 was assumed statistically significant. The statistical calculation was based on $2^{-\Delta\text{Ct}}$ values.

2.2 Craniofacial malformations

2.2.1 Animals and treatments

Sexually mature (8-week old) female and male CD1 mice (Charles River, Calco, Italy) were used. At arrival they were housed 4 per cage and acclimatised for 7 days and kept in controlled standard conditions ($T=22\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$; humidity= $55\pm 5\%$; light from 6a.m. to 6p.m.) throughout the study. All selected procedures were in accordance with the Italian law (D. Lgs n° 2014/26, implementation of the 2010/63/UE) and approved by the Animal Welfare Body of the Università degli Studi di Milano and by the Italian Minister of Health. Food and water was provided ad libitum before and during the whole experimental period.

At mating 4 females per male were used. In order to minimize inter-litter stage variability, the short-period mating will be selected: 4 females were transferred in the male cage for 2 hours in the morning. Mating was determined by the presence of a vaginal plug (considered day 0 of gestation, E0). When considered pregnant, the pregnant mice were randomised for distribution over groups. Mice and cages were identified with a colour code. At day of treatment (E8) mice were orally exposed to azoles by gavage or were injected i.p. with valproic acid. Mixture groups were both orally

and i.p. treated. Dams were sacrificed by CO₂ overdose at term of gestation (E18). Litters were also identified with a mark in the colour belonging to the group. Moreover, the position in the uterus was marked.

Additional animals per top dose level group were included for an interim sacrifice at day 9 (E9) of pregnancy and embryos evaluated in order to detect developmental stage and any abnormality. Embryos were processed for gene expression or immunostaining.

For PBPK modelling maternal blood and liver were collected both at E9 and at E18. Placenta and foetal liver were collected for two foetuses per litter (foetuses in the position proximal to the ovary).

Treatment groups were as follows: Females considered pregnant (vaginal plug detected) were randomly assigned to the different experimental groups using the GraphPAD QuickCalcs software. The assigned colour code has been used to assist with visual recognition of different group animals.

Cyproconazole (Sigma-Aldrich, Italy. Product number 46068, purity \geq 98.0%): 0-25-50-75-100 mg/kg per os (gavage, in DMSO: corn oil 1:9. Treatment volume: 0.2 mL/pregnant mouse).

Triadimefon (Sigma-Aldrich, Italy. Product number 45693, purity \geq 98.0%): 0-100-200-300-400 mg/kg per os (gavage, in DMSO (Sigma-Aldrich, product number 8001-30-7): corn oil 1:9. Treatment volume: 0.2 mL/pregnant mouse).

Valproic acid (sodium valproate, Sigma-Aldrich, Italy. Product number P4543, purity \geq 98.0%): 0-150-200-300-400-500-600 mg/kg (intra-peritoneal injection, in saline. Treatment volume 0.3 mL/pregnant mouse).

(C) + triadimefon (T): 0- (C12.5+ T50)- (C25+ T100)- (C37.5+ T150)- (C50+ T200) mg/kg per os (gavage, in DMSO: corn oil 1:9. Treatment volume: 0.2 mL/pregnant mouse).

Cyproconazole (C) + valproic acid (V): (C0 + V0)- (C12.5+ V150)- (C12.5+ V200)- (C25+ V200)- (C37.5+ V250)- (C50+ V300). Cyproconazole: per os (gavage), in DMSO: corn oil 1:9. Treatment volume: 0.2 mL/pregnant mouse. Valproic acid (sodium valproate): intra-peritoneal injection, in saline. Treatment volume 0.3 mL/pregnant mouse.

2.2.2 Parameters evaluated

From arrival till sacrifice, animals were monitored daily. At E8, after treatment, animals were monitored during the first three hours in order to evaluate any sign of adverse effects. Body weight was registered at E0, E8 (the treatment time), E14, E18 (the sacrifice time at term of gestation). At sacrifice (CO₂ overdose) a general necroscopic evaluation was performed on dams. Litter weight (uterus with the content), foetal weight and placental weight were recorded. Post implantation loss index ($[(\text{number of resorptions} + \text{dead foetuses})/\text{number of implants}] * 100$) was calculated in all dams. Foetuses and placentae were externally examined under a dissecting microscope. Any abnormality (including cleft palate) recorded. After euthanasia, foetuses were processed for the double staining of the skeleton (head) according to the method described by Kimmel and Trammell, 1981 or fixed in Bouin fixative (body). At E9, embryos were explanted from uteri, examined under a dissecting microscope in order to detect the developmental degree (number of somites) and any developmental delay or abnormality and processed for immunostaining (fixation in Dent's fixative) or gene expression (frozen in liquid nitrogen for the -80°C storage) for the evaluation of specific biological markers. The chosen markers were Crabp1; Cyp26a1; Cyp26c1; Dlx5; Hoxa2; Hoxa3; Hoxd4; Krox20.

2.3 Steatosis

2.3.1 Animals and treatments

The in vivo study was carried out at the Fraunhofer Institute for Toxicology and Experimental Medicine (ITEM, Hanover, Germany). The study design followed the OECD TG 407). Adult 6-week old Wistar rats (strain CrI:WI) (Charles River Laboratories, Sulzfeld, Germany) have been used after 1 week of acclimatisation. Animals were housed in Makrolon® (polycarbonate) cages type III, two rats of the same sex and dose group per cage, and were maintained under conventional laboratory conditions (constant 12-hour light/dark cycle with controlled temperature at 22 °C ± 2 °C and a relative humidity at 55 % ± 15 %). Commercial food (Ssniff V1534; Ssniff-Spezialdiäten, Soest, Germany) and tap water were offered ad libitum. Animals were randomly divided in groups (N=4) and were provided with food and water ad libitum. Animals were daily observed for body weight, food intake, water intake, clinical signs, and behaviour. At the end of the 28-day treatment animals were euthanised.

Dose selection was based on available literature data and data from EFSA evaluations. For each substance, the most reliable NOAEL was chosen as the lowest dose level and starting point for further dose selection (NOAEL; imazalil and thiacloprid : 10 mg/kg bw, clothianidin 100 mg/kg bw). The maximal dose for each compound was chosen based on the same studies (thiacloprid: 140 mg/kg bw; imazalil: 120 mg/kg bw; clothianidin 100 mg/kg bw). All other doses were evenly spaces between the NOAEL and maximal dose. Following the EuroMix approach for testing single compounds in equipotent mixtures relative potency factors has to be estimated. Thus, the maximal doses of single compounds were used for RPF calculation due to the absence of quantifiable data regarding the lipid accumulation in in vivo studies or PBTK models to extrapolate. RPFs were determined as follows; thiacloprid is 2.50 times more potent than clothianidin (RPF 1), while imazalil is 2.92 times more potent than clothianidin (RPF 1). In comparison to thiacloprid (RPF 1), imazalil is 1.16 times more potent (RPF 2.92/ RPF 2.50).

Treatment groups were as follows (daily by gavage):

Imazalil: 10, 38, 65, 93, 120 mg/kg bw

Thiacloprid: 10, 43, 75, 108, 140 mg/kg bw

Clothianidin: 100, 163, 225, 288, 350 mg/kg bw

Imazalil + clothianidin: 5+15, 19+55, 33+95, 46+135, 60+175 mg/kg bw

Thiacloprid + imazalil: 21+18, 38+32, 54+46, 70+60 mg/kg bw mg/kg bw

Thiacloprid+clothianidin: 5+13, 21+53, 38+94, 54+134, 70+175 mg/kg bw

Control: vehicle 7.5 ml/kg bw

Compounds were emulsified in 0.5% carboxymethyl cellulose/deionised H₂O.

One day after the last administration of the test and reference items, the animals were killed and prepared for histopathological examination and further analyses. Before narcosis, the rats were treated intraperitoneally with heparin (1000 U/rat i.p.). Afterwards, they were anaesthetized with pentobarbital, the thoracic cavity was opened, a whole body perfusion with rinsing solution (10 min with saline at 4°C: flow 110 mm mercury column = 150 cm water column = 0,146 bar) was applied and the rats were killed by cutting the *vena cava caudalis*.

2.3.2 Parameters evaluated

The adverse outcome analyses finished and evaluated so far includes changes in the body and organ weights histopathology examination, analysis of the hepatic lipid content via GC-FID and residue analysis in liver and kidney tissue. The procedures of the respective analyses are described below. Further examinations like PB-BK modelling, analysis of the lipid content of the blood via GC-FID triglyceride, quantification of the histopathological findings as well as MoA-related investigations via next generation sequencing, qPCR and WB are still in progress and will not be reported in this deliverable.

2.3.2.1 Body and organ weight change

Individual body weights were recorded to the nearest 0.1 g once a week throughout the study for all animals. Terminal body and wet organ weights were recorded upon necropsy. The following organs were taken, weighed and preserved: liver, kidney, heart, thymus, spleen and brain.

2.3.2.2 Histopathology

Histopathological examination was done for the liver at the Fraunhofer Institute for Toxicology and Experimental Medicine (ITEM, Hanover, Germany). Therefore, standard histology analysis was performed: liver lobes were fixed in a 5% formaldehyde solution and the tissue samples were dehydrated and subsequently embedded in paraffin (Leica, Germany), cut into slices of 3-5 µm and stained with hematoxylin/eosin. Following the histological sampling, the rest of the lobes was cut into small cubes (approx. 5 x 5 mm), cleansed on filter paper and shock frozen in liquid nitrogen immediately and stored in tubes (-80°C).

2.3.2.3 Analysis of hepatic lipid content by GC-FID

Small pieces of frozen tissue were homogenized under liquid nitrogen. The tissue powder was transferred into RLT buffer (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany), mixed immediately (approx. 20 mg tissue powder/ml buffer) and stored at -80°C. Triglycerides were extracted according to a method described by Hutchins et al. (2008).

For calibration of the retention times of the triglycerides, a triglyceride standard mixture (palm kernel triglycerides, BCR 632 A, Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, USA) was added to each sequence.

2.3.2.4 Compound analysis in tissue

At study termination the residue concentrations of the three pesticides in the liver as well as in the kidney were analyzed by a certified commercial laboratory (SGS, Institute Fresenius, Berlin, Germany) using the accredited method ASU L 00.00-115 LC 115, LC (DIN EN 15662).

2.4 Results

2.5 Endocrine effects, feminization

Anogenital distance (AGD) was modulated clearly by Flutamide, possibly by Dienestrol, but not by Linuron. Regarding the effects of exposure to the mixtures, AGD was affected by Flutamide+Dienestrol and Flutamide+Linuron mixtures and possibly by Dienestrol+Linuron mixtures (Fig. 2).

With respect to nipple retention at PND14, Flutamide alone, as well as combined with Dienestrol and Linuron, caused significant nipple retention of treated pups. On the contrary, neither Dienestrol nor Linuron alone or in combination significantly affected this parameter. Cryptorchidism showed some occurrence in Flutamide -alone or in mixtures-, but not after treatment with either Dienestrol or

Linuron. Cryptorchidism did not result a sensitive endpoint in our study, although more in depth data analysis is ongoing.

Testis tissue was collected for gene expression analysis (qRT-PCR) of: CYP17a1, Insl3, StAR, Cyp11a1, Pgr and HSD3 β . Analysis of single compounds is completed and results for at least four of the genes are as expected. Analysis of mixture experiments is still ongoing.

Analyses of blood samples for dienestrol concentration have been completed and the results are being analysed for their incorporation in the PBPK modelling.

2.6 Craniofacial malformations

2.6.1 Morphological observations

After E8 treatment, the three selected molecules (cyproconazole, triadimefon, valproic acid) were able to induce dose-related effects on conceptuses. At term of gestation (E18) cranio-facial defects (cleft palate, facial cleft, ablepharia, tongue protrusion) were observed. The morphological evaluation of embryos at midgestation (E9) revealed typical abnormalities at the branchial apparatus level (branchial arches reduced or fused). Groups exposed to the mixtures showed a dose-related increase of cranio-facial abnormalities (Fig. 3). The comparison with the effects of the single substances do not reject dose-additivity hypothesis. Expression and distribution of biomarkers suggested an abnormal migration of neural crest cells into the branchial structures.

2.6.2 Kinetic parameters and confirmation of PBPK modelling

A PBPK model has been developed for cyproconazole in mice, and plasma measurements, performed 24 hours after dosing of the dams, have been used to confirm the modelling. As shown in Figure 4 the measured data (green bullets) after treatment with 100 mg/kg bw are consistent with the PBPK model. In addition, the peak (C_{max}) concentration derived from the confirmed model have been estimated to be 13.7 (7.6-23.1 mg/l) corresponding to 47 (26-79) μ M. The incidence of craniofacial malformations at this dose was >50%. This is in good agreement with the WEC data (see table 2 of Deliverable 3.3) that show >50% incidence of brachial arch malformations at concentrations >20 μ M.

2.6.3 *In vitro* and *in vivo* RPFs

In vitro RPFs have been calculated from table 2 of Deliverable 3.3 and, using cyproconazole as Index Compound, they are: triadimefon 0.9 and VPA 0.03. Based on *in vivo* data they are: triadimefon 0.25 and VPA 0.34. These *in vitro* vs *in vivo* differences can be explained by differences in kinetics as suggested by the PBPK models (for cyproconazole figure 3, for triadimefon figure 4.8.1 of Deliverable 4.1 and for VPA figure 4.9.1 of Deliverable 4.1). Table 2.1 reports the relevant data. It appears that the expected C_{max} concentration after treatment with the same dose (column B) varies and when corrected for the RPF as derived from *in vitro* WEC assays (column D) their ratio (column E) is consistent with the *in vivo* RPFs (column F).

Compound (A)	C _{max} (μ M) after 100 mg/kg bw (B)	<i>In vitro</i> RPF (C)	<i>In vitro</i> RPF normalized C _{max} (μ M) (D)	<i>In vivo</i> RPF based on C _{max} (E)	<i>In vivo</i> RPF – experimental data (F)
Cyproconazole	47	1	47	1	1
Triadimefon	6	0.9	5.4	0.12	0.25
VPA	500	0.03	15	0.32	0.34

2.7 Steatosis

2.7.1 General toxicity and changes in body and organ weights

During and after treatment, the rats were carefully inspected. After one week of treatment some animals in the high or/and very high dose groups showed treatment-related body weight losses. Thus, during the first half of the administration period body weights were statistically significantly decreased in the thiacloprid very high dose group and the clothianidin high and very high dose group as well as in the thiacloprid + clothianidin very high dose group. Some of these animals were found dead or had to be killed in moribund condition. Overall, six animals were lost within the first half of the 4-week administration period. At termination of the study (29 days) no statistically significant changes in body weight, as compared to vehicle controls were observed (see Table 1) for the remaining animals.

Concerning changes in organ weights, the absolute and relative wet weights of livers were increased in all pesticide-treated groups (with statistical significance in all high and very high dose groups (see Table 1). The highest liver weight changes were observed in the thiacloprid + clothianidin and imazalil + clothianidin mixture groups with an increase in the relative liver weight of about 57% and 55% (compared to the control group), respectively. Overall, the increases in liver weight were higher in the mixture treatment groups than in the groups treated with the single compounds. For all other organs no statistically significant changes as compared to vehicle controls were observed.

2.7.2 Liver histopathology

Firstly, as treatment-related finding a dose-dependent centrilobular hepatocellular hypertrophy was detected, mostly in the mid to very high dose for all pesticide-treated groups (observations very slight to moderate). This change correlated with the liver weight increase (see Table 1).

Secondarily, no lipidosis (steatosis) was found in any of the animals, neither in the control groups nor in one of the six pesticide-treated groups.

Furthermore, other findings such as the extramedullary hematopoiesis and mixed inflammatory cell infiltration occurred in some animals of every group (control and treatment groups; observations very slight to slight) and are considered to be incidental findings unrelated to the treatment.

All animals which were killed in a moribund condition exhibited a diffuse slight to moderate congestion, which is most likely due to the cardiac arrest.

2.7.3 Hepatic lipid content

The repeated 28-day oral treatment of the rats with the single compounds as well as with the binary mixtures led to decreased triglycerides levels in rat livers (see Table 1). All three single pesticides induced a mostly dose-dependent decrease of triglycerides with the strongest effect for triglycerides with 50 C-atoms in the fatty acyl chains (in total) and the weakest for triglycerides with 56 C-atoms in the fatty acyl chains. The strongest decrease in the single compound treatment groups was seen for clothianidin. All treatments with the binary mixtures also showed a mostly dose-dependent decrease of triglycerides, showing again the strongest effect for triglycerides with 50 C-atoms in the fatty acyl chains and the weakest for triglycerides with 56 C-atoms in the fatty acyl chains and the following potency THI+CTD > CTD+IMZ > THI+IMZ.

2.7.4 Pesticide levels in selected organs

Following 28-day repeated oral treatment with the single substances, residue concentrations were detected in the liver in the following order: thiacloprid (7.5 mg/kg, very high dose) > clothianidin (2.5 mg/kg, very high dose) > imazalil (0.13 mg/kg, very high dose). In kidney, tissue residues were approximately in the same range for Thiacloprid (7.2 mg/kg, very high dose), while for clothianidin the tissue residues were higher than in the liver (5.7 mg/kg, high dose). Overall, for imazalil very low residues concentrations or even below the LOQ were detectable, in both liver and kidney.

Following exposure to the binary mixtures, a tendency for higher residue amounts as for the single compounds was found in both liver and kidney. The strongest effects were observed for the mixture treatment thiacloprid + clothianidin with an increase in residues in the liver tissue of about 3-fold for thiacloprid and 9-fold for clothianidin (both very high dose group) compared to the residues in the single compound treatment. In kidney tissue the increased amounts for the treatment thiacloprid + clothianidin are about 2-fold to 7-fold higher for thiacloprid and clothianidin, respectively.

3. Conclusions

In these EuroMix *in vivo* toxicity studies three different molecules were tested as single compounds as well as in binary mixtures to assess their mixtures effects *in vivo* following the EuroMix compound based approach by considering relative potencies of the tested compounds.

3.1 Endocrine effects, feminization

Available data so far allows the conclusion that dose-additivity model cannot be rejected for compounds with dissimilar mode of action and that AGD appears to be the more sensitive and reliable parameter to assess anti-androgenic/estrogenic activity *in vivo* as compared to nipple retention and cryptorchidism. Moreover, *in vitro* (and *in silico*) data correctly predicted the *in vivo* AO. More detailed conclusions will be reachable when all gene expression data will be analysed.

3.2 Craniofacial malformations

The overall evaluation of results indicate that the single treatment during the early postimplantation period (E8) is able to alter the cranio-facial morphogenetic program, inducing specific abnormalities at the cranio-facial structures. Dose-dependent effects were registered both for single substances and for mixtures. Dose-additivity was not rejected both in the case of molecules sharing a similar molecular initiating event and for molecules with different molecular initiating events acting on the same pathway. Embryonic evaluation at midgestation showed branchial apparatus as target structures. This is also consistent with the WEC results (morphology and gene expression). In addition, initial analysis indicates that PBPK modelling can predict *in vivo* RPFs from the RPFs estimated in the appropriate *in vitro* model (WEC)

3.3 Steatosis

The following observations based on the parameters which are completely evaluated so far. Analysis concerning like PBPK modelling of the toxicokinetic behaviour, quantitative evaluation of liver histopathological findings as well as MoA-related investigations like gene expression analysis are still in progress.

Regarding the changes in organ weights a treatment-related significant increase in liver weights was detected, with the highest effects for the clothianidin mixture groups. Generally, the increase in liver weights was higher for the mixture treatment groups than for the single compound treatment groups. This finding may indicate cumulative effects for the tested single compounds in mixture. Furthermore, this increase in liver weight might be correlated with the observed dose-dependent centrilobular hepatocellular hypertrophy for all treatment-groups in histopathological examination.

Additionally, the levels of the compounds in liver and kidney tissue differed clearly in the following order THI > CTD > IMZ. These findings are consistent with published literature (Yokota et al. 2003) as well as JMPR reports (JMPR clothianidin 2010, Metruccio, F. and Boobis, A.; JMPR thiacloprid 2006, Pfeil, R., Tasheva, M.; available: <http://apps.who.int/pesticide-residues-jmpr-database>) and the EFSA DARs for the individual substances. All three substances showed a rapid absorption, broad distribution in the organs as well as excretion. While clothianidin is moderately metabolized,

thiacloprid and especially imazalil are extensively metabolized. For imazalil the amount of parent compound detected in urine was below the LOQ after 24 h of exposure which might explain the very low to below LOQ amounts of residues found in our analysis. For thiacloprid significant higher levels were found in high dose female rats (48 h after exposure to 100 mg/kg bw) which indicate a delayed absorption or excretion of thiacloprid in this group.

Tissue levels after co-exposure were generally higher than after treatment with the single compounds, indicating possible metabolic interaction at high doses.

In summary, first hints for compound interactions of the three pesticides clothianidin, imazalil and thiacloprid in binary mixtures as well as for hepatotoxic effects were observed. The hypertrophy as a main effect in histopathological examination should be further investigated in a quantitative manner as well as on molecular level by e.g. qRT-PCR analysis of target genes to elucidate if the observed hypertrophy indicates steatosis in an early stage.

3.4 General conclusions

After the complete evaluation of all investigated parameters the comparison of the result obtained *in vivo* and *in vitro* have the potential to answer questions regarding the potential of in the *in vitro* bioassay toolbox for refining assumptions in current cumulative risk assessment strategies.

As a general comment, the experience gained from the *in vivo* studies indicate that dose additivity cannot be rejected also in case of combined exposures to compounds acting with a dissimilar mode of action (i.e. with a different MIE a possibly some KEs of the AOP). However, this applies to combined exposures to individual doses that even alone cause (or are very close to) some effect while relevant human exposures occur well below such levels. So, this needs to be considered a provisional conclusion until studies will be performed at the inflection point of the dose-response curve. These studies require a high number of data points and, therefore, can only be performed (and ethically justified) with *in vitro* assays such as those used in the EuroMix project. Consequently, to ensure the applicability of these assays to the entire organism there need to be bridging data between *in vitro* and *in vivo* as it has been done in the EuroMix Project. The data need to be understood within an AOP or a network of AOPs that really reflect the events occurring *in vivo*. Thus, AOP-wise testing was performed within the EuroMix project. AOPs can identify knowledge gaps, and therefore may guide testing. Beside numerous opportunities, there are still some misconceptions, pitfalls and limits of applicability. For example AOPs describe toxicodynamics, but not toxicokinetics. They are structured in linear relationships without feedback mechanism reflection. Furthermore they don't address species to species variations, *in vivo in vitro* variations as well as internal and external dose issues. The results obtained in the EuroMix project, in fact, point out to the need of a confirmation of the AOP and related *in vitro* assays before their full application: while in the case of craniofacial malformations and feminisation *in vitro* assays are consistent with the AO, the data on steatosis indicate limited consistency with the AO in the whole organism. Finally, PBPK modelling appears as an appropriate approach to estimate *in vivo* RPFs from *in vitro* RPFs.

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Figure 1: Endocrine effects, feminisation: scheme of the treatment of animals

Fig 2. AGD of rat pups at PND0/1, PND4, PND7, PND14 and PND21.

Table 1: Preliminary summary of the results of the 28-day oral toxicity study in female Wistar rats.

Parameter		Thiacloprid	Imazalil	Clothianidin	Thiacloprid + Imazalil	Thiacloprid + Clothianidin	Imazalil + Clothianidin
Body weight	Terminal total body weights	-	-	-	-	-	-
Organ weight	Relative liver weight	↗	↗	↗	↗	↗	↗
	Relative kidney weight	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Relative adrenal gland weight	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Relative spleen weight	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Relative thymus weight	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Relative lung weight	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Relative heart weight	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Relative brain weight	-	-	-	-	-	-
Liver histopathology	Congestion	-	-	↗	-	-	-
	Extramedullary hematopoiesis	↗	-	-	↗	-	-
	Hypertrophy	↗	↗	↗	↗	↗	↗
	Inflammation	↗	↗	↗	↗	↗	↗
	Steatosis	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Necrosis	-	-	-	-	-	-
Hepatic lipid content (GC-FID)	Triglycerides	↘	↘	↘	↘	↘	↘
Compounds analysis	Liver	+	+	+	+	+	+
	Kidney	+	-	+	+	+	+

↗ increase; ↘ decrease; - no effect/not detected; + detected

Figure 3. Cranio-facial abnormalities in fetuses exposed to mixtures of cyproconazole and triadimefon (A) or cyproconazole and sodium valproate (B).

A) black Cyproconazole, red Triadimefon, green Mixture

B) black Cyproconazole, red sodium valproate, green Mixture

Figure 4: PBPK model of cyproconazole in mice following oral dosing of 100 mg/kg bw. Mean (red line) with confidence intervals (blue line) of plasma concentration. The green dots represent measured values from the *in vivo* experiment.

